

NEXTGEN

PROTEINS

Bioconversion of Underutilized Resources into Next Generation Proteins for Food and Feed

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Lead author/editor Sjokovin

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Contributors

Authors	Organisations name	E-Mail
Sveinn Agnarsson	Sjokovin	sveinn@sjokovin.fo
Hanna-Leena Alakomi	VTT	Hanna-Leena.Alakomi@vtt.fi
Jaakko Paasi	VTT	Jaakko.Paasi@vtt.fi
Marie Shrestha	TTZ	MShrestha@ttz-bremerhaven.de

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable proposes the following policy recommendations:

Boost consumer acceptance

Consumer acceptance is a major challenge for many producers of alternative proteins. Although consumers may be willing to accept alternative proteins in feed applications (aquaculture, broilers, pet food), they are much more hesitant when it comes to food. As consumer health is of utmost importance, thorough information must be provided on toxicology, microbiological and chemical safety, nutritional value, sustainability (carbon footprint, LCA), and quality of the new proteins. The food industry, both individual firms and associations, is in a key position to provide scientific, up-to-date and robust information to consumers, in collaboration with national authorities, consumer associations, and other stakeholders.

Guide consumer choices

Consumer choices should be guided towards more sustainability dietary patterns through behavioural interventions and nudging. The price gap between alternative proteins and more conventional proteins can also be shortened through changes in incentives, making the more sustainable choices more affordable for consumers.

Encourage farmers' diversification

Farmers must be encouraged to diversify their protein production. Collaboration should be fostered between farmers and food producers and other food industry partners. Awareness should be raised among farmers to produce for human consumption. Policy instruments are needed for financial support for farmers for lost income as they change crops, as well as new investment in infrastructure, capacity building and training, and help in finding new markets.

Develop sustainable food strategies

Member states should develop food strategy and dietary guidelines that incorporate all aspects of sustainability. EU can help coordinate. Politicians should be engaged and able to explain why it is necessary to develop new protein sources, although other sources already exist.

Structure comprehensive policy

Public agricultural support policies in the EU must be adjusted to better serve modern food systems. Due to historical reasons, the policies are largely focused on certain products and mainly support farming practices that are currently understood to have large negative environmental impacts. As the markets for food and feed are highly price sensitive, the support systems are skewing the markets, giving competitive advantage to proteins produced with EU-support and putting proteins receiving little or no support at a disadvantage. These policies are not well aligned with the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy, although the new CAP 2023-2027 is a step in the right direction. A stronger reform is though necessary to restore parity between all sustainable sources of protein for food. In order to accelerate the transition to sustainable food systems it is essential to employ all available policy instruments – legislation, funding through various programs, public procurement – to integrate management perspectives across policy areas.

Improve the balance between regulation and innovation

The EU regulatory food framework is based on the principles of safety, the precautionary principle and the risk analysis principle. The EU safety assessment environment is one of the most detailed in the world, but the emphasis on consumer safety may be delaying the protein transition. A better balance is needed between regulation and innovation.

Globally harmonise regulations

There is a currently considerable difference between the regulatory framework in the EU and other countries. Of crucial importance here is the longer time it generally takes European producers to have a novel food product authorised. European firms thus find themselves in a disadvantageous position and unable to compete with firms operating elsewhere. This can both slow down innovation within the EU and encourage firms to relocate outside Europe. Globally harmonising novel food regulations would reduce this trade barrier and put European firms on a more equal footing.

Speed up authorisation

Applying for authorisation for novel food on the EU market is time consuming and expensive. The scientific requirements and safety assessment are similar in the EU, US and other countries, but the basis of approval is quite different, and the authorities outside Europe are swifter in processing applications for novel food. More resources are needed for the authorisation process and EFSA and/or the process must be speeded up.

Strengthen financial incentives and support

Large firms may seize opportunities for novel food to acquire a monopoly during the five years they hold exclusivity in the market. Financial incentives and support should be more readily available for SMEs seeking authorisation for novel food, as well as for first field trials which are always risky. As the volumes in field trials may be high, the trials can be very expensive and may even lead to substantial losses. Smaller firms should also be encouraged to collaborate on novel food applications, jointly put together data and share the costs, as they will then have more facilities for production if and when the novel food is authorised.

Develop a top-down approach

Rather than individual applicants submitting application of a novel food for a specific use, the authorities should make public a list of novel foods identified as feasible for production, and the requirements and conditions that should be met in each case. This would not preclude firms for submitting applications for different novel foods, but the top-down approach could speed up the production of alternative proteins and thus the transition toward a more sustainable food system.

2 Introduction

Over the next three decades, a growing global population, rising average income and living conditions, and increasing urbanisation are expected to increase the demand for food by 50%. An ageing population and more interest in healthy diets will further increase the demand for protein. However, the current level of protein production, both animal and vegetal-based is unsustainable, and has severe negative environmental impacts in terms of greenhouse gas emissions, land and water use, and biodiversity loss. The negative impacts of climate change on agriculture will put additional strain on the global food system.

The EU is not self-sufficient when it comes to proteins. According to the EU protein balance sheet for 2022/2023, 77% of the crude protein used for feed is produced in member states, but 23% imported (European Commission, 2022). Although all roughage – grass, silage maize, fodder legumes and dried fodder – used for feed, which makes up 42% of the total feed use in EU, is produced within the EU, the self-sufficiency rate is lower for crops and non-plant sources, and only 39% for co-products. Most importantly, only 3% of protein sources from soya is produced in EU, and 26% of protein from oilseed.

It is therefore of vital importance to find sustainable alternative protein sources that can be economically produced in quantities that meet growing food and feed sectors. Alternative proteins are proteins which include various plant protein (e.g. soy, wheat, and pea), insects (e.g. crickets and black soldier fly), microbial protein (e.g. algae, fungal, bacterial and yeast), and cultured meat or other cellular agriculture products. While some of these sources are known to European consumers, others are more novel.

Although alternative proteins still only make up a small portion of the world production of protein, the market has been growing fast, especially the demand for plant-based proteins, and is expected to continue along that path, with the North American market leading the way. Alternative protein has both been used in food and feed, but because of high prices many of these protein sources have not been competitive.

This deliverable builds on work undertaken in the work package on Safety and Legal Requirements (WP1) and other work packages of the NextGenProteins project, and has the primary aim of putting forward policy recommendations. These recommendations have emerged from discussions with project partners and stakeholders outside the consortium, as well as analysis of the EU regulatory framework and policy.

3 General EU Policy Framework for alternative proteins

3.1 The European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy

The EU has adopted and implemented several policies in recent years that should have an impact on the production of alternative proteins (AP) in Europe in the coming years. EU leaders set the tone in 2019 by adopting the European Green Deal that aims to make Europe

the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 and reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels (European Commission, 2019.).

The Farm to Fork strategy was published later in the spring of 2020 (European Commission, 2020b). The strategy, which is a part of the European Green Deal, aims to make the European food system more sustainable across different dimensions and to reduce its impact on third countries. In particular, the strategy aims to accelerate the transition to a sustainable food system that should:

- Have a neutral or positive environmental impact
- Help to mitigate climate change and adapt to its impacts
- Reverse the loss of biodiversity
- Ensure food security, nutrition and public health, making sure that everyone has access to sufficient, safe, nutritious and sustainable food

Figure 1. Cornerstones of the Farm to Fork Strategy.

The strategy also sets out both regulatory and non-regulatory initiatives, with the common agricultural policy (CAP) and common fisheries policy (CFP) as key tools to support a just transition.

The strategy's main goals (see Figure 1) are to:

- Ensure sufficient, affordable and nutritious food within planetary limits
- Halve the use of pesticides and fertilisers and sales of antimicrobials
- Increase the amount of land devoted to organic farming
- Promote more sustainable food consumption and healthy diets
- Reduce food loss and waste

- Combat food fraud in the supply chain
- Improve animal welfare

The Farm to Fork Strategy foresees a number of initiatives and legislative proposal, among other on organic farming, front-of-pack nutrition labelling and sustainable food labelling, and food waste reduction. An action plan on organic farming was presented by the EC in March 2021, with the main goal to boost organic production to reach 25% of the EU's agricultural land use by 2030 (European Commission, 2021). Member states have also been encouraged to develop national organic farming plans.

The Biodiversity Strategy was launched in May 2020, with the long-term plan to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems (European Commission, 2020c). The two strategies complement each other, but also share some targets, such as the aim to increase production of organic food and cutting pesticide use.

The Farm to Fork Strategy also aims to legislative Framework for Sustainable Food Systems (FSFS) which should be adopted by the Commission by the end of 2023 (European Commission, n.d.). FSFS goal is to accelerate and make the transition to sustainable food systems easier. One of the core objectives is the promotion of policy coherence at EU level and national level, mainstream sustainability in all food-related policies and strengthen the resilience of food systems.

The Farm to Fork Strategy clearly spells out the need for increased production of both plant protein and alternative proteins. Thus, it stresses the need to foster EU-grown plant protein as well as alternative feed materials such as insects, marine feed stocks (e.g. algae), and by-products from the bio-economy (e.g. fish waste). For this purpose, well-targeted support for the algae industry is envisioned.

One of the key issues of the Farm to Fork strategy is to ensure sustainable food production. For this purpose, the strategy focuses on the circular bio-based economy as still a largely untapped potential for farmers and their cooperatives. It is noted that biorefineries that produce biofertilizers, protein feed, bioenergy, and biochemicals offer opportunities for the transition to a climate-neutral economy. To enable this transition, the strategy also points out that a key area of research will be to increase the availability and source of alternative proteins, such as plant, microbial, marine and insect-based proteins and meat substitutes.

3.2 The European protein strategy

Discussions have been taking place within EU for several years on how to expand protein production in Europe, but such a strategy has not yet been formally adopted. A draft report on European protein strategy has though been developed by the European's Parliament Committee on Agriculture and Rural Development and will probably be adopted in early 2024 (European Parliament, 2023). According to the draft, the EU protein strategy should be based on:

- A vision for increased protein production
- Better conditions for protein production in the EU

- The development of plant-based and alternative protein for food and feed
- A holistic approach that includes the whole food value chain
- Concrete policy actions

The 13 policy actions put forward include a novel food legislation that simplifies and speeds up the authorisation processes, and a directive on waste that allows more types of biodegradable waste to be considered as feed and that allows food production residues to be used and transported. Further, the strategy draft also calls for a clear research and development funding strategy to promote and stimulate the market uptake of plant-based proteins for food and feed in the EU.

In October 2022, The European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) adopted an opinion on what additional aspects should be taken into account when formulating such a European protein strategy (EESC, 2022). To also meet the objectives of strategic supply autonomy, EESC recommended that the strategy should include the following:

- Fostering research and innovation in the area of plant-based proteins along the entire value chain and for need-oriented and optimised use of plant-based protein sources
- Developing and more strongly promoting protein potential in the EU
- Strengthening a sustainable domestic production of plant-based proteins, produced in accordance with the high European standards
- Developing and expanding regional value chains and regional processing capacities
- Continuously collaborating with institutions and agricultural organisations to promote the cultivation and use of domestic plant proteins in the food and feed industry
- Further increasing crop potential by improving and broadening breeding strategies
- Expanding education and advisory services and knowledge transfer
- Enabling and facilitating protein-crop production on ecological focus areas
- More strongly linking livestock farming with regional feed potential
- Consistently complying with existing limit values for pollution caused by emissions (nitrate in surface and ground water, ammonia, etc.); internalising external costs
- Promoting particularly animal-friendly farming practices through consumer information and product labelling
- Setting production and quality standards addressing the health and environmental impact of imports of products competing with those produced in the EU
- Running an information campaign in parallel on the consequences that different dietary habits have on the environment and health

3.3 The Common Agricultural Policy

CAP was launched in 1962 as a partnership between agriculture and society, and between Europe and its farmers (European Commission, n.d). The primary aims of the policy are to provide affordable, safe and high-quality food for EU citizens, ensure a fair standard of living

for farmers, and preserve natural resources and respect the environment. The policy has evolved over the years and on January 1st 2023 the CAP 2023-27 came into force (Regulation (EU) 2021/2115). In the New CAP, each member states must design a national CAP strategic plan, combing funding for income support, rural development, and market measures. While EU specifies the common objectives and funding guidelines, each member state has considerable discretion over their implementation.

The reformed CAP (see Figure 2) aims to provide more targeted support to smaller farms, while enhancing the contribution of agriculture to EU environmental and climate goals. The policy will also allow member states more flexibility in adapting measures to local conditions.

Figure 2 Key objectives of the CAP 2023-27

The CAP is divided into two pillars, where the first consists of decoupled direct payments, eco-schemes, and coupled income support. The second pillar consists of various rural development measures. The eco-schemes are a novelty but they are not mandatory for farms. Under the New CAP, member states are obliged to reserve 25% of direct payments for eco-schemes, which may for instance be dedicated to climate, water, soil, and biodiversity interventions, as well as animal welfare measures, to support organic measures or for forestry (Becker et al., 2022).

The EU's Cohesion Policy complements rural development policy in many regards. The 2021-2027 has set out five policy objectives (Regulation (EU) 2021/1058).

1. A more competitive and smarter Europe
2. A greener, low carbon transitioning towards a net zero carbon economy
3. A more connected Europe by enhancing mobility

4. A more social and inclusive Europe
5. Europe closer to citizens by fostering the sustainable and integrated development of all types of territories

These priorities will be supported by the European Regional Development Fund, The European Social Fund, the Cohesion Fund, the Just Transition Fund, and the Interreg programs.

As one of the main building blocks of Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) was adopted in March 2020 (European Commission, 2020a). The measures that will be introduced under the action plan include making sustainable products the norm in the EU, and empowering consumers and public buyers. The measures will focus on the sectors that use most resources and where the potential for circularity is high, such as food, water and nutrients.

While these funds may support both farmers, cooperatives and SMEs, there are also other EU vehicles that may cater better to the financial needs of SMEs.

4 Regulatory framework for safe Food and Feed in the EU

In order to ensure food safety, it is important to consider the whole food chain from farm to fork. All the aspects and players within the supply chain, starting from the production of animal feed and primary production, through production, distribution and sales of food to the consumers influence food safety.

NextGenProteins has summarized EU food and feed laws previously in D1.1 and D1.2. EU law regulates the conditions for food and feed business operators to produce and commercialise their products in the European Union. Notably, EU policymakers have adopted – in the early 2000s – a package of legislative texts which define general principles and standards in the area of food and feed safety. These legislative texts are most known as the ‘General Food Law’ (Regulation No 178/2002) and the ‘Hygiene Package’ (e.g. Regulation No 853/2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs and Regulation No 1831/2003 laying down requirements for feed hygiene).

According to the above texts, food or feed business operator – are responsible for ensuring the safety of the marketed products: To this end, these texts impose general obligations on those actors – such as the registration or approval of their activities before national competent authorities – and establish hygiene standards to be applied at the different stages of production covered.

The European food safety regulatory framework provides EU consumers with one of the safest food systems in the world (Table 1). The EU agency, European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) provides independent trustworthy scientific advice and communicates on existing and emerging risks from farm to fork (EFSA, n.d)

The new regulation on the transparency and sustainability of the EU risk assessment in the food chain, has been in application since 27 March 2021 and strengthens the EFSA’s ability to carry out its risk assessment functions in accordance with the highest transparency standards (Regulation 2919/1381)

The aim of the regulation was to increase the transparency of risk assessment in the food chain, to strengthen the reliability, objectivity and independence of the studies submitted to EFSA, and reinforce the governance of EFSA to ensure its long-term sustainability. The transparency regulation stipulates that:

- Citizens will have access to studies and information submitted by industry in the risk assessment process. Stakeholders and the general public will also be consulted on submitted studies.
- EFSA will be made aware of all commissioned studies to guarantee that companies applying for authorisations submit all relevant information. The Authority will also offer advice to applicants prior to the submission of dossiers.
- The European Commission may ask EFSA to commission additional studies and may carry out fact-finding missions to verify that laboratories/studies comply with quality standards.

Table 1. General objectives of food and feed law in the European Union (https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/general_food_law/principles).

General objectives of food and feed law
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Guarantee high level of protection of human life and health and the protection of consumers’ interests”. • “Guarantee fair practices in food trade, taking into account animal health and welfare, plant health and the environment”. • “Ensure free movement of food and feed manufactured and marketed in the Union, in accordance with the General Food Law Regulation”. • “Facilitate global trade of safe feed, and safe, wholesome food by taking into account international standard and agreements when developing Union legislation, except where this might undermine the high level of consumer protection pursued by the Union”. • Implement risk analysis (risk assessment, risk management and risk communication) in decision-making

4.1 Novel food in EU

Novel Food is defined as food that had not been consumed to a significant degree by humans in the EU before 15 May 1997, when the first Regulation on novel food came into force (Regulation (EC) No 258/97. 'Novel Food' can be newly developed, innovative food, food produced using new technologies and production processes, as well as food which is or has been traditionally eaten outside of the EU. The updated version of the regulation – Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 - was published in 2015 and was fully implemented in January 2018.

The underlying principles underpinning Novel Food in the European Union are that Novel Foods must be:

- Safe for consumers.
- Properly labelled, so as not to mislead consumers.
- If novel food is intended to replace another food, it must not differ in a way that the consumption of the Novel Food would be nutritionally disadvantageous for the consumer.

The Novel Food authorization process follows the general pattern of other regulated food products in the EU. The EFSA panel on Nutrition, Novel Foods and Food Allergens (NDA) performs the assessment. In the assessment process both the safety and nutritional aspects of the novel food are emphasized.

The Novel Food consultation process is defined in article 4 of regulation (EU) 2015/2283 and the implementing regulation (EU) 2018/456. The novel food status is decided by the competent authority of the Member State, in which the applicant intends to introduce the food into the market for the first time. Annex II of the regulation (EU) 2018/456 provides detailed instructions concerning the information that should be presented in the technical dossier accompanying the consultation process. The focus is in the composition of the food and the extent and history of its use in the EU. The outcome of the consultation is published on the Commission website (European Commission, n.d.). Pre-market authorisation of Novel Foods on the basis of an evaluation in line with the above principles is necessary.

4.2 Novel Food application process in the EU

Food business operators can place a novel food on the European Union market only after the Commission has processed an application for the authorisation of a novel food, and has adopted an implementing act authorising the placing on the market of a novel food and updating the Union list. Thus, before placing a novel food on the European Union market, the applicant must first submit to the Commission an [online applicationEN●●●](#) for authorisation in line with the requirements of Article 10 of the new Regulation. For submission of the dossier EFSA also provides detailed guidelines (EFSA, 2021).

Regulation (EU) 2019/1381 on the transparency and sustainability of the EU risk assessment in the food chain amended Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and the new regulation. Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/2469 has also been adjusted by Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/1772 to accommodate those changes. These new provisions are relevant to applications submitted from 27 March 2021.

If the novel food is liable to have an effect on human health, the Commission will request the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to carry out a risk assessment. EFSA carries out its safety assessment based on risk analysis. Dossiers need to contain data on the compositional, nutritional, toxicological and allergenic properties of the novel food as well as information on respective production processes, and the proposed uses and use levels. EFSA has provided guidance on the preparation and submission of an application for authorisation of a novel food in the context of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283(Revision1) (EFSA NDA Panel, 2021). According to the transparency regulation EFSA requires study notifications from the applicants, as shown in Figure 3.

EFSA will adopt its opinion in 9 months from the date of receipt of a valid application from the Commission. Within the seven months from the date of the publication of the EFSA's opinion, the Commission shall submit to the Standing Committee on Plants, Animals, Food and Feed a draft implementing act authorising the placing on the market of a novel food and updating the Union list. Once the act receives a favourable vote from the Standing Committee and is adopted and published by the Commission, the novel food can be lawfully placed on the European Union market (EFSA, n.d.)

The authorisation and entry for a novel food in the Union list includes, where appropriate: Specifications, conditions of use, additional specific labelling requirements and post-market monitoring requirements.

Novel food is subject to the general labelling requirements laid down in Regulation (EC) No 1169/2011. Specific additional requirements for the labelling of a novel food may also apply, if necessary, to properly inform the consumer. The label must mention the name of the food, and, where appropriate, specify the conditions of use. Any nutrition and health claim should only be made in accordance with the requirements of the Health and Nutrition Claims Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006.

The Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/2470 establishing the list of novel foods compiles all the authorised novel foods in the European Union to date. It includes their conditions of use, labelling requirements, and their specifications. All authorisations are generic and the Union list serves as a reference for economic operators who wish to place in the market an authorised novel food unless data protection is requested by the applicant (European Commission, n.d.). The Union list is updated by the Commission to add newly authorised novel foods. The summaries are listed in chronological order.

Figure 3 Novel food procedure according to EFSA. Source: [Novel food and traditional food applications | EFSA \(europa.eu\)](https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/food/novel-food)

In the EU, the length of the novel food process is generally between 8 to 18 months, with a possibility of clock stops if additional information is needed from the applicant. In some other regions/parts of the world the process is shorter, e.g. in Singapore where processing of novel food applications takes from 9 to 12 months and study notifications are not required. In Singapore the applications are confidential (Singapore Food Agency, n.d.).

In accordance with the requirements laid down in the Novel Food regulation (EU) 2015/2283, the European Commission will make the summary of the application publicly available based on the information concerning the name and address of the applicant, the name and

description of the novel food and scientific evidence demonstrating that the novel food does not pose a safety risk to human health.

The authorisations of novel foods under the former novel food regulation were addressed specifically to the applicant and gave the applicant exclusive rights to the novel food. With the current novel food regulation, although the specific authorisations, the conditions of use, the specifications and the labelling contained in them remain valid, they are no longer applicant-specific but have become generic following their inclusion in the Union list. This enables any food business operator to place the authorised novel foods in the European Union market. However, the regulation also grants an individual authorisation for five years, based on newly developed scientific evidence and proprietary data.

5 Focus of the NextGenProteins project

The primary aim of NextGenProteins (NGP) is to optimise the production of three alternative proteins (AP) and verify their use in various feed and food applications in order to meet customers' needs and ensure consumer acceptance (NextGenProteins, n.d.). The project contributes to strengthening food security, sustainability and self-sufficiency of EU protein production by demonstrating the suitability and economic viability of next-generation proteins as part of food and feed value chains; with less strain on natural resources and reduced environmental impacts.

5.1 Alternative proteins considered and their respective production processes

The proteins are produced from microalgae, single cells (SCP) and insects. The microalgae are grown on carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from a geothermal power plant in an efficient, indoor production process, the insects are grown on underutilised plant-food biomass, and in the case of single cells, carbohydrates derived from wood biomass and biomass residues are transformed through microbial fermentation into proteins. In all three cases, waste or underutilised resources are transformed into protein meal (see figure 4).

When NextGenProteins was launched in October 2019, the project consortium included four protein producers; Arbiom, Entocube, Mutatec, and VAXA, but Entocube ceased operation and went bankrupt in 2022.

[Arbiom](#) has developed technology to convert wood residuals into a protein-rich feed ingredient comprised of SCP (NextGenProteins, 2023a). The product, SylPro, has been authorized as a feed ingredient (Regulation (EU) No. 68/2013) and is considered as a non-novel food ingredient according to a Novel Food Consultation (Ref. Ares (2022) 476788).

[EntoCube](#) has developed technology for rearing edible insects, in particular crickets (Grylloidea), from which protein can be extracted. Frozen and dried formulations from whole house crickets (*Aceta domesticus*) are allowed as a feed for poultry and pigs and as novel food (Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/5 (NextGenProteins, 2023b).

[Mutatec](#) has developed techniques for producing, rearing and breeding black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*). The protein produced is only allowed for use in feed (NextGenProteins, 2023c).

[VAXA](#), previously known as Algaenovation Iceland, operates a microalgae facility, and produces protein streams from spirulina that can be used both in feed and food (NextGenProteins, 2023d).

Figure 4 Sustainable production of alternative proteins in the NextGenProteins project

The proteins produced by members of the NGP consortium have both been tested as feed and food. For feed, dose-response and field trials have been carried out on broiler chicken, turkey (Sirri et al., 2023; Zampiga et al., 2023) and aquaculture species (salmon, sea bream) and novel high-quality food products containing the alternative proteins have also been developed. Emphasis has been placed on improving the sensory quality of products through formulation technologies for increased consumer acceptance.

5.2 Consumer acceptance for NextGenProteins alternative proteins

A large online survey on the attitudes of European consumers towards alternative protein sources and processes as well as food containing alternative proteins was undertaken in the NGP project in summer 2021 (Arvola et al, 2021). The survey was conducted in six European countries; Finland, Germany, Iceland, Italy, Poland, Sweden, and UK, with a total of 6600 consumers taking part.

According to the survey, European consumers, in general, trust most actors in the food value chain (trust indicated here as a mean of all answers), with consumers having highest trust in

small food producers and farmers. Clear mistrust was only evident towards the food industry, with consumers in Germany showing significant mistrust. Arguments towards trust or mistrust were not requested.

In the survey, consumers’ attitudes towards protein sources and processes under development in the NGP project as well as their application in food were requested. The attitudes were mostly positive or neutral, but 10-20% of the respondents did though have negative views towards torula and spirulina proteins, and 30 – 50 % in the case of house crickets.

Respondents’ positive attitudes were largely based on expected positive consequences for sustainability. A substantial number of consumers, 30 – 40 % of respondents, did though not know what to think because of novelty and unfamiliarity of these concepts. Accordingly, many consumers do not have strong negative prejudices or preconceptions towards these production methods and ingredients.

The positive overall attitude, however, does not directly turn into positive attitude towards the use of NextGenProteins proteins in foods. Thus, although NextGenProteins concepts are regarded as a good thing in principle, consumers seem to have relatively low belief in personal benefits related to the use of NGP proteins. This is in line with other studies done on consumer acceptance towards alternative proteins and comparisons with meat protein (Onwezen et al., 2021).

The results from the survey, show that just like in other studies, there exists a consumer segment that could be defined as ‘true believers’. These consumers have highly positive attitude towards AP and frequently use food that includes such proteins. That segment is growing fast.

5.3 Circularity, LCA, prices and risk for NextGenProteins alternative proteins

The circularity potential of the production processes of the three proteins considered – microalgae, SCP, and black soldier fly – was assessed using three indicators; circular resources, circular energy, and circular water (Agnarsson et al., 2022a). Circularity was considered under two scenarios, base scenario and circular scenario, where the former was defined according to the current operating conditions of each case study. The circular scenario for each case study was then developed according to the circular options with the highest likelihood of application as well as for key inputs. As shown in Table 1, VAXA uses a near-circular technology for production of microalgae, but the production of the other alternative proteins considered in NGP have the potential to reduce the environmental impacts from traditional protein.

Table 1 Circularity potential of NGP proteins

	Circular resources	Circular energy	Circular water
Microalgae	97%	100%	99.5%
SCP	86%	78%	76%
Black soldier fly	75%	90%	100%

The life cycle analysis (LCA) of the three alternative proteins was calculated using the circularity assessment for each case (Agnarsson et al., 2022a). As shown in Table 2, the carbon footprint ranged between 0.9 and 23.5, lowest for crickets, and highest for microalgae. By comparison the carbon footprint of beef (26% protein) is 110.5, but that of fishmeal from anchovy (63-65% protein) is 2.1. The water footprint was 0.03-3.46 m³, whereas that for beef is 9.12 and 0.17 for fishmeal from anchovy. The land use is miniscual, compared to 88 m² for beef and 0.0058 for fishmeal.

Table 2 Carbon footprint, water footprint, land use and carbon footprint Pareto drivers.

Protein Source	Scenario	Carbon Footprint (CF) (kgCO ₂ eq.)	Water Footprint (m ³)	Land use (m ² a)	Carbon Footprint Pareto drivers
Algae	Base	23.5	0.15	0.00039	Nutrients (63%) Electricity (34%)
	Circular	23.1	0.15	0.00039	Nutrients (63%) Electricity (34%)
SCP	Base	12.3	0.29	0.00027	Glucose (46%) Ammonia Nitrate (37%)
	Circular	3.4	0.06	0.00004	Heat (38%) Ammonia (35%) Electricity (10%)
Black Soldier Fly	Base	10.2	3.46	0.00074	Heat (62%) Biogenic inputs (38%)
	Circular	9.1	0.03	0.00037	Heat (69%) Biogenic inputs (30%)
Cricket	Base	0.9	0.15	0.00006	Nutrients [Gluten, oat, barley (85%)]

As pointed out in the deliverable (Agnarsson et al., 2022a), the relatively high carbon footprint of some of the NGP proteins is likely due to each case study evaluated in the form of pilot projects, and production had not been scaled up.

All protein producers are currently operating at a rather small scale and selling their products at higher prices than their main competitors. The value-chain risk assessment undertaken clearly revealed that producers are most concerned about the inability to attract operating capital and whether consumers will accept their products. (Agnarsson et al., 2022b) The former are risks that all innovative SMEs face, while the latter is typical for firms producing alternative proteins from novel sources, such as insects.

5.4 Challenges encountered in the frame of the NextGenProteins innovation project

The regulatory status of Torula was uncertain at the beginning of the NGP project and it was only relatively late in the program that it became clear that SylPro, the product of Arbiom, could be considered as a non-novel food ingredient. This affected development as food producers could not work with it in their production facilities.

Fair Insects BV was the only producer approved for production of house crickets and as the company was not a part of the consortium, this placed the production of house crickets by EntoCube into jeopardy.

Consumer testing in NGP was affected by the fact the food authorities in different European countries have different interpretations of the use of insects in food products. This misalignment should be corrected.

Gathering accurate and comprehensive data from the protein producers taking part in NGP was challenging, as the quality and quantity of data varied across different partners, reflecting the different stages of development of their respective protein production processes. Ensuring consistency in the data received was imperative as the varying quality of the data could potentially impact the accuracy of the analysis undertaken.

Each protein production process has unique characteristics and requirements. Gaining a deep understanding of these processes, including their energy requirements and specific steps, was a challenge, not least because in some cases it was difficult to identify the inputs used in certain processes. In many cases it was also hard to determine the specific employment requirements for each production process, i.e. understanding the number of people needed and the specific skills required. The challenge of scaling up the production processes was evident, as this calls for more complete information on differences in inputs and outputs for a scaled-up process.

Understanding and accounting for the resource limitations, such as the dependence on fresh water or fertile land, posed a challenge when considering the sustainability of the production process.

Mapping the upstream and downstream value chains for each protein production process was a complex task. This includes understanding the supply chain risks, market risks, and regulatory risks associated with each value chain. Linked to this is the need to gain a deep understanding of the main competing protein products in the market. This includes understanding their production processes, nutritional content of the product, and market positioning.

Creating models to compare the alternative proteins with conventional proteins is a complex task. This includes understanding the nutritional content, production processes, and environmental impacts of each type of protein.

Developing food products containing alternative proteins that consumers would accept proved quite difficult. Odour, flavour, and the appearance of the ingredients was not always desirable and difficult to mask. Huge efforts were also required to overcome some of the difficulties associated with the functional properties (e.g. water holding capacity). This task is challenging as the desired properties must be obtained without risking the economic viability of the production process.

The Covid-19 pandemic raged during much of the lifetime of the project and the restrictions implemented caused some delays. Mandatory working from home limited hands-on-work, and made collaborations between partners difficult, especially the interaction between protein producers and those engaged in the production of feed and food products.

6 Necessary Stakeholder engagement in the development of the NextGenProteins policy recommendation

Throughout the project, discussion have taken place with partners in NextGenProteins, and stakeholders have also at various levels of this project been directly and indirectly engaged in the policy recommendation process. The first steps were taken when representatives from the industrial partners participating in NGP were interviewed (Alakomi et al., 2020a; Alakomi et al., 2020b). The companies included VAXA, MUTATEC, EntoCube, ARBIOM, Naturalleva, Amadori, Waitrose, Grímur kokkur, and BIOZOON.

The interviews revealed that the firms view consumer health of primary importance and scientific information on toxicology, microbiological and chemical safety, and quality of the new proteins is needed. Consumers, farmers, and other stakeholders should be educated about the new protein sources, especially about sustainability, LCA, safety and nutritional value. Novel proteins might be more accepted by consumers in feed applications than in food products. Associations could be beneficial in providing information and training.

Traceability and labelling of products is important, not least because of possible allergens. Organic certificate would benefit industrial partners – and consumers – both in feed and food applications.

There is a difference between the regulatory framework in EU and other countries (e.g. Australia, Canada, Japan, Singapore, UK, US) and this can be regarded as a trade barrier and thus harm the competitiveness of European firms. Harmonizing the global novel food regulations could therefore level the playing field.

As part of the work undertaken in the work package on Regulation, Safety and Legal requirements (WP1) a survey was conducted among stakeholders outside the NextGenProteins consortium. Representatives from NextGenProteins reached out to 69 stakeholders – ministries, authorities, associations – both at national and international (EU) level. Interviews were then conducted with 30 of these, while the other 39 did not wish to be interviewed. The results from this survey are reported in deliverable D1.4 that was not included in the description of action (DoA). This additional deliverable will be made public.

Among other, respondents were asked to identify the largest challenges in term of regulation of alternative proteins. Representatives of food authorities taking part in the survey generally found the regulatory framework quite satisfying, and emphasised that although the process was long, sufficient research was needed in order to assure safety of the products. New complex products and novel foods could be challenging for surveillance and monitoring, and therefore training and education of control authorities was essential.

By contrast, industry stakeholders found the novel food regulations hindering innovation and harming the competitiveness – research, knowledge, technology, and business – of European firms. One interviewee noted that “the novel food regulation and the GMO regulation are the biggest stops in the system. It takes time and requires economic strength from a company that is interested in developing these kinds of products”. Another noted that as innovation always go much faster than what regulation can adapt to, the authorities will always be playing catchup.

Additionally, in the frame of the Horizon4Proteins collaboration, initiated in 2021 with the sister projects ProFuture, Smart Protein and Susinchain, a joint Policy Brief has been drafted to present solutions towards a more resilient food system (pending publication). The content was discussed in a dedicated session titled “Let’s talk about alternative proteins: Horizon4Proteins policy brief discussion” at the COP27 (<https://food4climatepavilion.com/event/thursday-10-november/>). It is expected that the Policy brief will be presented at the final event of ProFuture in September 2023.

In November 2022 NextGenProteins organized a joint co-creation [workshop](#) in Finland with the [FoodSafety4EU](#) project called: “How to improve communication and increase public engagement around alternative proteins”. The highlights of the discussions were: Openness, transparency, and traceability of food products are important. In addition to research, every actor in the food chain has its own responsibility for communication and increasing consumer trust. The whole value-chain also needs to have a harmonised message to consumers.

In May 2023, NextGenProteins initiated and took part in organizing together with Horizon4Proteins partners and EU representatives an online Policy Roundtable on the topic: “Unlocking the potential of alternative proteins in the EU: Diversification, environmental performance and competitiveness”. A recording of the event may be found here: [H4P Policy Roundtable](#).

7 NextGenProteins Policy recommendations

7.1 Boost consumer acceptance

Consumer acceptance is a major challenge for many producers of alternative proteins. Although consumers may be willing to accept alternative proteins in feed applications (aquaculture, broilers, pet food), they are much more hesitant when it comes to food. As consumer health is of utmost importance, thorough information must be provided on toxicology, microbiological and chemical safety, nutritional value, sustainability (carbon footprint, LCA), and quality of the new proteins. The food industry, both individual firms and associations, is in a key position to provide scientific, up-to-date and robust information to consumers, in collaboration with national authorities, consumer associations, and other stakeholders.

7.2 Guide consumer choices

Consumer choices should be guided towards more sustainability dietary patterns through behavioural interventions and nudging. The price gap between alternative proteins and more conventional proteins can also be shortened through changes in incentives, making the more sustainable choices more affordable for consumers.

7.3 Encourage farmers' diversification

Farmers must be encouraged to diversify their protein production. Collaboration should be fostered between farmers and food producers and other food industry partners. Awareness should be raised among farmers to produce for human consumption. Policy instruments are needed for financial support for farmers for lost income as they change crops, as well as new investment in infrastructure, capacity building and training, and help in finding new markets.

7.4 Develop sustainable food strategies

Member states should develop food strategy and dietary guidelines that incorporate all aspects of sustainability. EU can help coordinate. Politicians should be engaged and able to explain why it is necessary to develop new protein sources, although other sources already exist.

7.5 Structure comprehensive policy

Public agricultural support policies in the EU must be adjusted to better serve modern food systems. Due to historical reasons, the policies are largely focused on certain products and mainly support farming practices that are currently understood to have large negative environmental impacts. As the markets for food and feed are highly price sensitive, the support systems are skewing the markets, giving competitive advantage to proteins produced with EU-support and putting proteins receiving little or no support at a disadvantage. These policies are not well aligned with the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy, although the new CAP 2023-2027 is a step in the right direction. A stronger reform is though necessary to restore parity between all sustainable sources of protein for food. In order to accelerate the transition to sustainable food systems it is essential to employ all available policy instruments – legislation, funding through various programs, public procurement – to integrate management perspectives across policy areas.

7.6 Improve the balance between regulation and innovation

The EU regulatory food framework is based on the principles of safety, the precautionary principle and the risk analysis principle. The EU safety assessment environment is one of the most detailed in the world, but the emphasis on consumer safety may be delaying the protein transition. A better balance is needed between regulation and innovation.

7.7 Globally harmonise regulations

There is a currently considerable difference between the regulatory framework in the EU and other countries. Of crucial importance here is the longer time it generally takes European producers to have a novel food product authorised. European firms thus find themselves in a disadvantageous position and unable to compete with firms operating elsewhere. This can both slow down innovation within the EU and encourage firms to relocate outside Europe. Globally harmonising novel food regulations would reduce this trade barrier and put European firms on a more equal footing.

7.8 Speed up authorisation

Applying for authorisation for novel food on the EU market is time consuming and expensive. The scientific requirements and safety assessment are similar in the EU, US and other countries, but the basis of approval is quite different, and the authorities outside Europe are swifter in processing applications for novel food. More resources are needed for the authorisation process and EFSA and/or the process must be speeded up.

7.9 Strengthen financial incentives and support

Large firms may seize opportunities for novel food to acquire a monopoly during the five years they hold exclusivity in the market. Financial incentives and support should be more readily available for SMEs seeking authorisation for novel food, as well as for first field trials which are always risky. As the volumes in field trials may be high, the trials can be very expensive and may even lead to substantial losses. Smaller firms should also be encouraged to collaborate on novel food applications, jointly put together data and share the costs, as they will then have more facilities for production if and when the novel food is authorised.

7.10 Develop a top-down approach

Rather than individual applicants submitting application of a novel food for a specific use, the authorities should make public a list of novel foods identified as feasible for production, and the requirements and conditions that should be met in each case. This would not preclude firms for submitting applications for different novel foods, but the top-down approach could speed up the production of alternative proteins and thus the transition toward a more sustainable food system.

Table 3. Policy recommendations of NextGenProteins project.

Recommendation	Bottlenecks	Argumentation
Boost consumer acceptance	Consumers not accepting alternative proteins	Consumer acceptance is a major challenge for many producers of alternative proteins. The food industry, both individual firms and associations, is in a key position to provide scientific, up-to-date and robust information to consumers, in collaboration with national authorities, consumer associations, and other stakeholders.
Guide consumer choices	Consumers not making the correct choices	Consumer choices should be guided towards more sustainability dietary patterns through behavioural interventions and nudging. The price gap between alternative proteins and more conventional protein can also be shortened through changes in incentives, making the more sustainable choices more affordable for consumers.
Encourage farmers diversification	Too little produced of alternative proteins	Farmers must be encouraged to diversify their protein production. Collaboration should be fostered between farmers and food producers and other food industry partners. Policy instruments are needed for financial support for farmers for lost income as they change crops, as well as new investment in infrastructure, capacity building and training, and help in finding new markets.
Develop sustainable food strategies	Incomplete national food strategy and dietary guidelines	Member states should develop food strategy and dietary guidelines that incorporate all aspects of sustainability. EU can help coordinate. Politicians should be engaged and able to explain why it is necessary to

		develop new protein sources, although other sources already exist.
Structure comprehensive policy	Misalignment between the various EU policies	Public agricultural support policies in the EU must be adjusted to better serve modern food systems. These policies are not well aligned with the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy. In order to accelerate the transition to sustainable food systems it is essential to employ all available policy instruments – legislation, funding through various programs, public procurement – to integrate management perspectives across policy areas.
Improve balance between regulation and innovation	Regulation hampering innovation	The EU safety assessment environment is one of the most detailed in the world, but the emphasis on consumer safety may be delaying the protein transition. A better balance is needed between regulation and innovation.
Globally harmonise regulations	Regulatory framework in EU harming competitiveness	There is a currently considerable difference between the regulatory framework in the EU and other countries. European firms thus find themselves in a disadvantageous position and unable to compete with firms operating elsewhere.
Speed up authorisation	Authorisation taking too long time	Applying for authorisation for novel food on the EU market is time consuming and expensive. The scientific requirements and safety assessment are similar in the EU, US and other countries, but the basis of approval is quite different, and the authorities outside Europe are swifter in processing applications for novel food.

		More resources are needed for the authorisation process and EFSA and/or the process must be speeded up.
Strengthen financial incentives and support	SMEs unable to finance novel food authorisations	Financial incentives and support should be more readily available for SMEs seeking authorisation for novel food, as well as for first field trials which are always risky. Smaller firms should also be encouraged to collaborate on novel food applications, jointly put together data and share the costs, as they will then have more facilities for production if and when the novel food is authorised.
Develop a top-down approach	Too few firms engaged in production of alternative proteins	Rather than individual applicants submitting application of a novel food for a specific use, the authorities should make public a list of novel foods identified as feasible for production, and the requirements and conditions that should be met in each case. The top-down approach could speed up the production of alternative proteins and thus the transition toward a more sustainable food system.

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